

THE ROLE OF DISTANCE LEARNING IN MEDICINE

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Abstract: *At present, increasing the efficiency of the educational process in medical universities is an urgent task. One of the ways to solve this problem is the introduction of elements of distance learning technologies, which allows you to implement new approaches to learning and optimize the educational process.*

Key words: *distance learning, common forms, medicine, distance learning technologies.*

РОЛЬ ДИСТАНЦИОННОГО ОБУЧЕНИЯ В МЕДИЦИНЕ

Аннотация: *В настоящее время повышение эффективности учебного процесса в медицинских ВУЗах является актуальной задачей. Одним из путей решения этой задачи является внедрение элементов дистанционных образовательных технологий, что позволяет реализовать новые подходы к обучению и оптимизировать образовательный процесс.*

Ключевые слова: *дистанционное обучение, распространённые формы, медицина, дистанционные образовательные технологии.*

INTRODUCTION

Distance learning is the interaction of students and teachers with each other at a distance, while such learning reflects almost all the components inherent in the educational process (methods, goals, organizational forms, content) and implemented by specific means of telecommunication technologies that provide for the interactivity of the process.

Distance learning is the ideal and most optimal form of postgraduate education and training, as it helps to solve a number of problems that already graduates have, for example, due to different work shifts and duty schedules for trained doctors, different approaches to work and study [1, 4, 5, 20].

Training a doctor in practical skills requires traditional face-to-face contact with teachers, but all theoretical training and decision-making exercises can take place remotely. Distance learning differs from distance learning by a more convenient information delivery system and the use of new technologies in the learning process, which allows you to expand the circle of course participants and also expand the thematic range of courses taught without compromising their quality [2, 3, 21, 25].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Studies show that the use of electronic learning systems with visualization tools contribute to a more successful perception and memorization of educational material, allow you to penetrate deeper into the essence of cognitive phenomena [2, 6, 22, 24].

After enrolling in the course, each of the trained medical universities is given a login and password for entering distance education.

Education using distance learning technologies appeared in the 18th century, when a regular and accessible postal service appeared in Europe. At that time, students received

assignments by mail, corresponded with teachers, passed an exam at a certain time, and wrote a scientific paper.

The beginning of the 20th century is characterized by rapid technological growth, the presence of the telegraph and telephone. But there are no reliable facts about their use in training. A significant breakthrough was made in the possibilities of distance learning by the advent of radio and television. However, television and radio had a big drawback - the lack of feedback.

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In the 1990s, satellite technologies began to actively develop.

Starting from the 21st century, the Internet began to spread widely, contributing to the popularization of distance learning in universities. It was possible to communicate and receive feedback from any student, wherever he was. As soon as the speed increased, various educational trainings and online classes began to be held [7,8, 17, 19, 26].

With the help of distance learning, the following tasks can be solved: familiarizing teachers from different regions with the experience and developments of the country's leading specialists in the field of new technologies in education. And then these teachers will be able to transfer the acquired knowledge, developments and experience to their direct students through communication via the Internet. This will drastically accelerate the transfer of best practices and significantly expand the degree of its dissemination and implementation in the educational process.

Distance learning in medical universities allows you to: save time; reduce the cost of training; the possibility of simultaneously teaching a large number of students; improving the quality of education through the use of modern technologies; instant access to voluminous electronic libraries and knowledge bases; create a unified educational environment.

Of course, when there are pros, there are always cons. The negative aspects of distance learning are: lack of communication between students and the teacher; distance learning requires strict self-discipline, and its result directly depends on the independence and consciousness of the student; lack of practice, without which it is difficult to fully master the subject being studied; good technical equipment is needed, but not everyone who wants to study has a computer and Internet access; the presence of strong motivation - only those who have a good idea of \u200b\u200bwhat they need it for can learn; there is no constant control over students [9, 10, 14, 16,18].

A normal distance education program should have a huge range of methods for delivering educational information to the student. The implementation of DO can be carried out both online and offline.

The most common forms of distance learning:

- Chat class - training events where all participants have simultaneous access to the chat and teachers and students (for example, skype).

- Web lesson - a distance lesson, seminar, conference, business game, laboratory work or other form of training session, which is conducted through telecommunications or other Internet opportunities.

- Teleconference - is carried out using mailing lists by e-mail. Educational teleconferencing is characterized by the achievement of educational objectives.

- Telepresence is an experimental type of distance learning, in which the student, being in another place at the computer, can see, hear and speak with the help of a robot. During the lesson, the teacher asks questions, and the student answers them [1, 11, 15].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Distance learning should be based on an appropriate work program and the capabilities of the Moodle learning environment. The training program includes:

- Resources - theoretical materials for study in the form of files, or in the form of links to external sites;

- Active elements - the organization of activities that go beyond learning using the resources of a distance course. Active elements are mainly understood as the organization of communication between students of distance learning (forum, chat, messaging, etc.). As well as the organization of knowledge testing (tests, assignments, etc.);

- tasks - tasks, the answer to which must be provided in electronic form (the answer must be sent in the form of one or more files), in particular, writing a curatorial sheet, the mental status of the patient (examined during the practical lesson), analyzing a scientific article, writing essays, creating presentations on topics;

- tests - the main means of knowledge control in the Moodle distance learning system. Presented by a small amount (10 -15) of test tasks for each topic of the lesson with one or more correct answers;

- poll - a mechanism that allows students to ask a question with a choice of one or more answers. Using a survey, you can find out the opinion of distance learning students on a particular issue.

CONCLUSIONS

The distance form of education for students of medical universities has the right to further existence and development as a source of additional information, a section for monitoring their theoretical knowledge and a balanced alternative to full-time education. This form of education makes it possible to effectively solve educational problems that are relevant today: lifelong learning, continuous vocational training, learning "without borders" and in an interactive mode, as well as promoting knowledge at a distance.

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